

THE PROTEIN CONTENT IN TENEBRIO MOLITOR

Mirzaeva D.A.

University Alfraganus, Faculty of Medicine, Department
of Pharmaceuticals and Chemistry
e-mail: m.dilobar@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10926785>

Abstract: In this article, survival coefficients of *Tenebrio molitor* F6 larvae were determined in three different compositions and sources of nutrients with different humidity (wheat bran, *Lemna minor* and flour *Azolla carolina*). *Tenebrio molitor* F6 larvae of the generation of variants TMO-2 and TMO-6 were grown on wheat bran with an average survival rate of 0.79, on duckweed flour - 0.50, on azolla flour - 0.64. It was noted that the survival rate of larvae grown on wheat bran was 15.5% higher than that of larvae grown on azolla, and it is advisable to explain the source not by the protein reserve, but by the amount of moisture in it. It was noted that the moisture content (9.58-10.12%) (protein 15%) in wheat bran was a factor in the high viability of the larvae compared to azolla (protein-27%, humidity 8.2%). Despite the easy protein synthesis in the body of larvae in duckweed flour (protein - 16.1%, humidity - 4.4%) compared to azolla flour, its content is 3.8% lower than that of azolla, due to the fact that survival the larvae in them were lower than in wheat and azolla. Therefore, along with the protein content, moisture is an important factor when choosing a food source. When summing the survival rates of larvae of the *Tenebrio molitor* F6 generation in the studied nutrient media, the average survival was calculated as 0.96. This means that based on the established ratios of wheat bran, duckweed and azolla flour, it will be possible to create a nutrient medium with a new content, high nutritional value and low cost.

Key words: *Tenebrio molitor*, yellow mealworm, edible insects, insects feed, fish feed, protein, amino acid, macrophytes, *Lemna minor*, *Azolla carolina*.

Introduction. Studying the economic and environmental aspects of food insects allows them to be widely used. In particular, the high protein supply of insects and the fact that they consume less food than other sources allow us to consider them as an economically sustainable alternative source. The production of protein products based on food insects is explained by a high economic profitability than the production of protein products based on livestock and poultry [Van Huis., 2013]. In particular, if at least 20 kg of corn and soybeans are required per kilogram of beef [Smil 2002], food insects such as locusts will need 2 kg of feed to produce one kilogram of protein [Khujamshukurov et al., 2016].

The practice of obtaining protein products from food insects and their use in poultry and fisheries has not yet become widespread in the Republic of Uzbekistan. There are several reasons for this:

First, as in world practice, it is difficult to study new food sources and apply them in everyday practice;

The second - the ethnic mentality of the local population is sharply affected;

Thirdly, the staff of consumer farms does not have enough information about food insects, their importance, nutritional value, ease of production and guidelines for their use in the religious beliefs of the local population;

Fourth, the manufacturing sectors were provided with sufficient sources of production and so on.

After the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1991), livestock, poultry and fishing developed rapidly, small enterprises were established, and the demand for nutritious and inexpensive food products at the local level grew several hundred times.

In particular, 600 tons of wheat used in the food industry in 2018 was allocated only to the fishing industry. The main reason for this is that, under local conditions, wheat does not stand out as a source of food and feed. In addition, high-protein crops such as barley, corn and soybeans are not grown as large plantations. In addition, fish products and their processing industry, sufficient for the production of fishmeal, are under development. In particular, it was planned to grow about 6-9 tons of fish in 1996-2009, 72 tons in 2010-2017, 82 tons in 2018, 150 tons in 2019 and about 200 tons in 2020.

Therefore, one of the most important tasks is the development of the fishing industry in the local context, the creation of a continuous feed base for this industry with high nutritional and nutritional value.

It is known that a large number of food products are used in the cultivation of food insect species. These include products such as soy flour, corn flour and bran, wheat bran or cereal products, flour and bran, depending on the conditions of the region in different countries. Since these products are mainly food for human consumption, one of the important tasks is the search and study of alternative sources of their replacement.

In 2001, the FAO noted that in Uzbekistan, based on macrophytes *Lemna minor* of the genus *Lemnaceae*, they can produce 7-15 t / ha / year [FAO, 2001], based on our scientific studies, it was proved that in Uzbekistan it is possible to obtain 154 t / ha / year wet biomass or 27.34 tons of dry weight [Khujamshukurov., 2011]. This is due to favorable weather conditions in

Uzbekistan, the fact that the number of sunny days is almost 308 days, the possibility of continued growth of macrophytes from March to November.

Therefore, when growing edible insects from macrophytes, the preparation of feed or feed additives and their widespread use in practice is of great scientific and practical importance.

Purpose of work. Study of the viability of *Tenebrio molitor* larvae (*Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae*) in macrophytes grown in Uzbekistan and the dynamics of their egg laying.

Research methods. Object of study. The sixth generation (F_6) *Tenebrio molitor* (*Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae*) was used, collected from the southern foothills of Uzbekistan and propagated under controlled conditions. In the course of the study, from the numbered larvae and beetles of *Tenebrio molitor* (128: larvae 108, 20 beetles) collected from nature, after visual observation, we selected 2 largest in size compared to others (TMO-2: 5.36 cm, TMO-6 : 4.83 cm), (F_1 variant), on the basis of which the *Tenebrio molitor* colony was formed. Growing conditions: wheat bran with a standard content (protein 14-15%, fat 0.8-1.0%), as well as *Lemna minor* from macrophytes (protein 16.1%, fat 2.8-3.1%) and used the dry biomass of *Azolla carolina* (protein -27.6%, fat-2.8-3.2%). Temperature 20-22°C. In this study, F_1 -based variants of TMO-2 and TMO-6 larvae based on F_6 variant were used to determine viability characteristics on various nutrient media that are produced by the protein and to study the rate of their laying. Variants of *Tenebrio molitor* TMO-2 and TMO-6 larvae were used as control for each other when analyzing protein formation in various nutrient sources. The duration of cultivation in all samples was 28 days. Determination of proteins. Method R. Scoups (1985) was used for protein purification. The amount of protein in the supernatant was determined by the standard Lowry method.

Results and its discussion. In this study, variants of TMO-2 and TMO-6 larvae based on F_1 variant obtained on the basis of F_1 were used to study the properties of protein formation in various sources of nutrients. Variants of *Tenebrio molitor* TMO-2 and TMO-6 larvae were used as controls for each other in the analysis of viability characteristics in various nutrient sources. It was observed that the larvae of the TMO-2 (F_6) variant have different levels of protein synthesis when grown in various feeds, including 30.89% in wheat bran, 38.65% in duckweed, and 31.48% in azolla. It was noted that when growing larvae of the TMO-6 (F_6) variant in nutrient media of the same composition, 31.15% of the protein was synthesized in wheat bran, 37.60% in duckweed, and

30.26% in azolla. According to the results of general nutrient media, 31.02% of protein synthesis in wheat bran, 38.13% in duckweed and 30.87% in azolla compared to dry matter.

According to a generalized analysis of the TMO-2 and TMO-6 variants from the *Tenebrio molitor* F₆ generation, larvae grown on wheat bran synthesized 6.98% more protein than duckweed and 0.15% more protein than larvae grown in azolla. It was found that the larvae of the TMO-2 and TMO-6 variant grown in duckweed synthesize 6.98% more protein than wheat bran and 7.26% more protein than the larvae grown in azolla. This can be explained, first of all, by the fact that flour based on azolla and wheat bran are more difficult to break down in the body of larvae than duckweed. Secondly, this can be explained by the insufficient moisture content in the flour based on azolla and the relatively low protein content in wheat bran. The fact that the larvae of the TMO-2 and TMO-6 variants from the F₆ *Tenebrio molitor* generation synthesized proteins with different characteristics in different sources of nutrients suggests the need to study the viability of these larvae in these nutrient sources. The viability characteristics of the larvae of the TMO-2 variant based on wheat bran are shown in Figure 2. When the viability of TMO-2 larvae in wheat bran was studied on the basis of 300 larvae (30 of them, 10 variants), it was noted that their average viability was 72.33%. The daily survival of larval variants was observed, while the average survival rate was 1.0% in the first ten days (results of 5-10 days) and a 5% decrease on the 15th day. On the 20th day of observations, the larval survival rate was 83% and decreased by 11% between 15 and 20 days. A further decrease of 9.33% was observed between 20–25 days of observation, while the decrease was 1.34% between 25–28 days, with an average survival rate of 72.33% in the medium. Thus, the average survival of the larvae of the TMO-2 variant in this nutrient medium was 0.72%. It was noted that the average survival of the larvae of the TMO-6 variant grown on wheat bran averaged 87.33%. When analyzing TMO-6 variant larvae in the variant section, it was found that the average survival rate in the first ten days was 99% on average and decreased to 94% on the 15th day of observation. In wheat bran, the larvae of the TMO-2 variant lost 17% viability in 20 days, while the larvae of TMO-6 lost only 7.67% over this period. The larvae of the TMO-6 variant lost viability by 11.33% by the 25th day of observation, while the TMO-2 variant lost viability by 26.33% at that time.

By the 28th day of observation, the larvae of the TMO-6 variant lost 12.67% of their viability, while by this time the TMO-2 variant lost 27.67% of their

viability. It was also noted that in the analysis from the point of view of the internal variants of TMO-2 and TMO-6, the TMO-2 variant lost 15% more viability than the TMO-6 variant. Therefore, it can be assumed that the adaptability of each larval variant to the composition of the nutrient medium will also vary. The analysis of the nutrient medium (wheat bran) showed that the generalized average survival of the larvae of the TMO-2 and TMO-6 variants was 79.83%. In wheat bran, the survival rate of larvae of the *Tenebrio molitor* F₆ generation can be estimated at 0.79%. It was noted that the larvae of the TMO-2 variant grown on the basis of duckweed flour lost less than 4% of viability in the first 10 days of observation compared with wheat bran. By the 15th day of observation, survival dropped sharply (25.33%). It was noted that survival was 19.33% higher than that of wheat bran. It was found that the larvae of the TMO-2 variant grown in duckweed lost about 40% viability by the 20th day of observation, while the loss of survival was 23% higher than that of wheat bran. After 25 days of observation, the survival rate of TMO-2 larvae grown in duckweed was 56.33%, which is 17.34% lower than the survival rate of larvae grown on wheat bran for 25 days. On the 28th day of the study, the survival rate of TMO-2 larvae grown on the basis of duckweed was 52.33%, which is 20% lower than that of wheat bran (28th day).

Analysis of the larvae of the TMO-6 variant on internal variants showed a 4.33% reduction in survival in the first ten days of the study. This indicator was 3.33% higher than for the TMO-2 and TMO-6 variants grown on wheat bran, and 0.3% higher than for the TMO-2 variant larvae grown on duckweed.

The overall survival of the larvae of the TMO-6 variant grown on the basis of duckweed was 48.67%. In addition, the viability of the larvae of the TMO-6 variant grown in azolla on the 15th day of observation was 73.0%, 20.0% lower than that of the larvae of the TMO-2 and TMO-6 variant grown on wheat, and 1.67% lower than the larvae of the TMO-2 variant grown in duckweed. On the 20th day of the study, the survival rate of larvae of the TMO-6 variant grown in duckweed was 64.33%, which is 23.17% lower than that of wheat bran and 4.33% higher than that of larvae of the TMO- variant 2 grown in duckweed. On the 25th day of observation, the average survival of larvae of the TMO-6 variant grown in duckweed was 61.33%, which is 19.84% lower than that of wheat larvae and 5.0% higher than that of TMO- 2 grown in duckweed. In the last 28 days of the study, TMO-6 was 3.66% less viable than TMO-2 grown in duckweed. The 28-day survival rate of the TMO-6 variant was 48.67%. This was 29.33% lower than the viability of the larvae of this variant in wheat bran. The fact that

the viability of a duckweed-based culture medium is lower than that of wheat bran can be explained by the very low moisture content in duckweed flour. The overall survival of larvae grown on the basis of *Azolla carolina* flour was 64.33%. In particular, the survival of TMO-2 variant larvae was 94.0% in the first ten days of growth and 79.33% on the 15th day of observation. This indicator was 14.67% lower than that of the larvae of the TMO-2 and TMO-6 variant grown on wheat bran, while it was found that it was 5.49% more viable than the larvae grown on duckweed.

Moisture (9.58–10.12%) in wheat bran (protein 15%) may have served as a factor in higher viability of larvae than in azolla (protein-27%, moisture content 8.2%). Although duckweed flour (protein-16.1%, humidity-4.4%) is poorly synthesized in the body of larvae, it is 3.8% less than that of azolla, which can be explained by the fact that the survival of the larvae is lower than that of wheat and azolla. In particular, the larvae of the TMO-2 variant showed 72.33%, the larvae of the TMO-6 variant showed a viability of 63.67% in wheat bran and an average of 79.83% in the nutrient medium.

This indicates that their survival in this culture medium is 0.79. It was found that the larvae of the TMO-2 variant grown on the basis of duckweed averaged 52.33%, the larvae of the TMO-6 variant were 48.67%, and the average viability by food sources was 50.5%. According to this food source, the larvae have a survival rate of 0.50. It was observed that the larvae of the TMO-2 variant grown in *Azolla* were 63.67%, the larvae of the TMO-6 variant were 65.0%, and the average survival for the food source was 64.33%. In this food source, the larvae survival was 0.64.

Conclusion. Usually in the production of *Tenebrio molitor* under controlled conditions and on the basis of which such expensive and inconvenient soya flour, wheat bran, corn bran, cornmeal, beer and alcohol bard, grape waste (cake) are used in the production of feed products. This suggests the need for alternative food sources to organize industrial production based on food insects. As such alternative sources of nutrients, macrophytes can be considered as one of the most viable options. Favorable climatic conditions in the Republic of Uzbekistan, sunny days at least 270 days a year, from March to mid-November, allow macrophytes (duckweed, azolla, eichornia, pistsiya, etc.) to be grown on an industrial basis. Based on our scientific studies, it was proved that 154 t/ha/year of wet biomass or 27.34 tons of dry weight can be obtained on the basis of *Lemna minor* in Uzbekistan [Khujamshukurov et al., 2011]. This will allow to establish the production of food insects in Uzbekistan and provide it

with a food base based on macrophytes. In our study, survival rates for *Tenebrio molitor* based on macrophytes in their wheat bran and macrophyte-based nutrient sources were reported. In particular, the survival rates of *Tenebrio molitor* F₆ larvae were determined in three different moisture compositions and sources (wheat bran, *Lemna minor*, and *Azolla carolina* flour). When the *Tenebrio molitor* F₆ larvae of the TMO-2 and TMO-6 generations were grown on wheat bran, the average survival rate was 0.79 ha, duckweed 0.50, and azolla flour 0.64. Summing up the survival rates of *Tenebrio molitor* F₆ larvae in the studied nutrient media, it was shown that the average survival was 0.96. This allows you to create a breeding ground with a new content, high nutritional value and low cost, based on the established ratios of wheat bran, duckweed and azolla flour. As a result, the production of feed based on feed insects *Tenebrio molitor* will provide the fast-growing fish industry in Uzbekistan with a source of continuous, full nutritional value. Growing these types of insects using macrophytes of duckweed and azolla, which are easy to breed, will reduce their cost and increase their nutritional value.

References:

1. FAO. 2001. Duckweed: A tiny aquatic plant with enormous potential for agriculture and environment. Food and Agricultural Organization, Geneva. Pp.108.
2. Khujamshukurov N.A. 2011. Alternative protein products. J. XXI-technology.4(5):14-15.
3. Khujamshukurov N.A., Nurmuxamedova V.Z. 2016. Production feed: modern trend and development aspect. Scientific overview. J. Zooveterinary. №8 (105):34-37.
4. Smil V. 2002. Food production. In the Nutrition Transition; Academic Press: San Diego, CA, USA. Pp.25-50.
5. Van Huis A., Van Itterbeeck J., Klunder H., Mertens E., Halloran A., Muir G., Vantomme P. 2013. Edible Insects: Future Prospects for Food and Feed Security (No.171). Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations: Rome, Italy, 2013.